

PROBLEMS OF ELIMINATING WRITTEN SPEECH DEFICIENCIES IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is discussed what methods should be used to improve the literacy of primary and junior school students, to overcome the shortcomings in their written speech and some obstacles in the correct pronunciation of sounds observed in them.*

Keywords: *written speech, K.N.Monakhov, O.V.Pravdina, speech defects, speech therapy.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИСПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДЕФЕКТОВ ПИСЬМЕННОЙ РЕЧИ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается, какие методы следует использовать для повышения грамотности учащихся начальных и младших классов, для преодоления недостатков в их письменной речи и некоторых препятствий в правильном произношении наблюдаемых у них звуков.*

Ключевые слова: *письменная речь, К.Н.Монахов, О.В.Правдина, дефекты речи, логопедия.*

Oral speech is used in direct communication with the surrounding people, while written speech is a means of communicating with people who lived in a different place and time in a different situation and to understand their thoughts. Written speech is the most convenient means of voluntary expression of our thoughts. Written speech consists of reading and writing processes. In order to understand written speech, it is necessary to acquire English in a special order, that is, to be literate. Written speech is formed on the basis of oral speech.

Due to the complexity of the mechanisms of written speech, there are various difficulties in its formation. In speech therapy, written speech defects are dysgraphia (Greek dis-disorder, grapho-write), agrophia (a-negation, no grapho-write), dilexia (Greek dis-disorder, lego I read), alexia (Greek a-denial to do, no, lego-reading) terms.

The authors of corrective pedagogy have created valuable theories about shortcomings in written speech. Kusmaul (1877), Berkan (1881) showed in their scientific works that reading and writing deficits are independent speech deficits. Until then, the deficits in written speech were considered to be one of the main signs of mental retardation.

Since the second half of the 19th century, the shortcomings in reading and writing are caused by the superficial and dissatisfied perception of the shortcomings, scientists recommended to name the shortcomings in written speech with the terms legosenia (slowness of reading) and graphosthenia (slowness of writing). In 1907, the Russian scientist K.N.Monakhov considered defects in written speech to be a sensory character of aphatic disorder related to sensitivity. The famous neuropathologist R.A. Tkachev and S.S. Mnukhin proposed to call them alexia and agrophia as speech defects caused by the inability to remember syllable images and incorrect pronunciation of sounds.

Deficiencies in written speech were identified by scientists M.Y.E. Khvatsev, R.Y.E. Levina, F.A. Rau, R.T. Voskis, S.S. Lyapidevsky, L.F. Spirova, N.A. Nikashina, O.A. Tokareva, O.V. Pravdina, V.G. Petrova, V.V. Voronkova, A.V.Yastrebova, G.A.Kashe and others

thoroughly studied them and considered them as defects arising from defects in oral speech and phonemic hearing.

The ability to analyze and synthesize speech, that is, to analyze and compose, appears in a child along with the formation of oral speech. Defects in oral speech prevent the development of written speech. A number of defects in written speech are observed in children who have difficulty pronouncing sounds correctly and distinguishing them from each other while listening. During reading and writing, they drop and replace letters.

Defects in written speech can also be related to the wrong perception of the shape of letters. In this case, the child confuses similar letters and their elements.

Dysgraphia and dyslexia due to writing defects are common among schoolchildren. It is recommended to study the errors observed in the written work of dysgraphists by separating them into certain groups. These are as follows: 1. Errors of a phonetic-phonemic nature - replacing similar sounds in terms of pronunciation (articulation) and perception (acoustics), for example: gul-kul, zina-sina, bog-pokh, daftar-taftal and etc. 2. Defects in word structure: a) replacement of syllables, for example: mashin-manashi, randa-radan; b) dropping vowels: grapevine, snake-ilm, cherry-glos, book-ktob, dropping consonants, for example: friendship-friendship, machine-maina, bayram-baram; g) not to write syllable words at the end, for example: boy-bol, olhori-olri, gilos-glos, lenta-leta, anor-ano; d) adding extra, unnecessary vowels or consonants, for example: stul-ustul, doska-dosika, duck-duck, bahar-bahhor, gilam-gigilam. 3. Splitting one word into two or adding two words, for example: Bahar keldi-Ba khorkeldi. 4. Writing letters similar in shape and spelling, their elements, for example: sh-i, t-p, l-m, i-sh, s-v, b-d, g-l, z-va, etc. Changing the positions of letter elements in space: s-z, v-u, s-e. 5. As a result of fine movement of hand muscles, motility disorders, writing letters incorrectly, not making lines in the notebook, writing syllables and words on top of words, and hakazo. 6. Grammatical errors (morphological, orthographic, syntactic, punctuation errors, etc.). In this case, because the child confuses the left and right sides, the letters are written as they are represented in the mirror, for example s-s, b-b, i-I, d-d.

Deficiencies in writing are observed together with dysgraphia, and in many cases, deficiencies in reading are observed together with dyslexia. Dyslexia is rare as an independent speech disorder. Symptoms of dyslexia are reading by turns; inability to connect letters to syllables; 2. Repeatedly repeating letters and syllables, omitting them, changing their place, not understanding, incorrect, slow reading; 3. Replacing parts of words, syllables, additions with other letters, syllables or words 4. Not observing punctuation marks, pauses, stopping in the middle of words and making pauses, reading the second part of the first word with the first part of the next word.

Reading is a type of speech activity that is closely related to the pronunciation and perception of sounds. In the literature on psychology, the mechanisms of reading are, firstly, the connection between the reading of the word, that is, the graphic side and the pronunciation, and secondly, the understanding of the meaning of the read word, that is, the conscious self. It is emphasized that winter is coming. In order for reading skills to be perfect, both sides of the reading process should be welded together and shaped. Otherwise, it is impossible to understand the material and provide conscious reading. Although the symptoms of dyslexia listed above are more related to reading technique, they all affect reading comprehension. The literature on speech therapy describes the ways and methods of eliminating dysgraphia, agraphia, dyslexia,

and alexia. L.I. Yefimenkova and I.N. Sadovnikova in the book "Ispravleniye i preduprezhdeniye dysgrafii u detey" suggest to eliminate dysgraphia in the following order: 1. Preparation period. During this period, it is determined to what extent the students have acquired the skills of reading and writing: the skills of analysis and synthesis are trained; auditory and visual analyzers, phonemic hearing, auditory and visual memory are developed. 2. Work is carried out on the separation of vowels and letters. 3. Consonant sounds and letters are separated from each other and differentiated. 4. Work on the word, give knowledge about the structure and composition of the word. 5. Work on the sentence. This logopedic method is designed to eliminate the shortcomings in written speech as a result of insufficiently developed phonemic skills of analysis and synthesis.

Speech therapist O.V. Pravdina recommended eliminating the shortcomings in written speech in three stages. At the first stage, it is recommended to carry out differentiation work on the basis of voiced and unvoiced, explosive p, t, k sounds and letters. At this stage, it is recommended to conduct preparatory articulation exercises and work on some grammatical concepts to teach pronunciation of complex sounds such as sh, j, l, r. In the second stage, it is planned to establish the pronunciation of sounds such as s, z, sh, s, ch, b, g, d, l, r, and work on automation and differentiation. Teaching to analyze and synthesize syllables, words and sentences should take the main place in every training at this stage. The third stage is a recommendation to consolidate (automation) and teach to separate (differentiation) the sounds taught to pronounce correctly in the first stages by developing connected oral and written speech. will be done.

Many speech therapists (M.YE. Khvatsev, R.YE.Levina, F.A. Rau, R.I. Lalayeva, I.K. Sadovnikova, L.N. Yefilinkova, R.M. Boskis, etc.) recognize the defects in written speech as a defect caused by the underdevelopment of oral speech, and who recommended the method of elimination through the development of oral speech, by consistently conducting special work on the entire speech system. Training on this methodology requires working on sounds, syllables, words, sentences and connected speech. However, the direction and content of these works are determined taking into account the general scope of knowledge, reading and writing abilities of people with written speech disabilities, what difficulties they have in reading and writing, what mistakes they make, and the reasons for their origin. L.F.Spirova and A.V.Yastrebova recommend eliminating the deficiencies in written speech observed in the speech of elementary school students by working on the entire speech system in three stages. In the first stage, the following work is planned on phonetics - phonemic component: 1. Formation of ideas about the structure of the word from sounds; 2. Development of phonemic learning and analysis-synthesis skills; 3. Eliminating pronunciation defects. At the first stage, it is necessary to develop children's attention and memory, to teach them to self-manage, to check, to teach them to answer questions clearly and completely. In the second stage, lexical-grammatical deficiencies are eliminated, and auditory perception is developed. In the third stage, work is carried out to consolidate the learned sounds, introduce them into the child's speech, and develop analytical skills. Thus, defects in written speech are considered one of the most complex speech defects. It is necessary to prevent these shortcomings with children of preschool age. From this, the development of the child's oral speech, spatial perception, memory, attention, analysis and synthesis activities, analysis of speech, work on vocabulary, development of the grammatical

component, elimination of shortcomings in oral speech, development of fine hand movements is particularly important.

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